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Coffee husk ashes as supplementary cement material

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Abstract: The objective of this work is to present the characterization of Coffee Husks Ashes (CHA) and evaluate its potential as Supplementary Cementitious Material (SCM). To achieve this purpose, X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) and modified Chapelle tests were performed in the CHA before different burning process. Semi-adiabatic calorimetry was used in order to assess the influence of different content of ashes (5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 %, bwoc), treated at 600 °C for 3 hours, on the hydration kinetics of pastes with a water to cement ratio of 0.4. XRF and Chapelle test indicates that the use of CHA as SCM needs some precautions regarding its dosage and matrix. Semi-adiabatic calorimetry test indicated an increase in accumulated heat as the level of CHA in the pastes increases.

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1. Introduction

The use of unconventional materials in the construction industry is constantly evolving, due primarily to the demand of modern society for the expansion of sustainable processes in the different branches of human activities [1]. It is known that the cement clinker production is responsible for a large part of the world's carbon dioxide emissions [2]. Aiming to minimize the harmful impacts on the environment due to the cement production, several natural residues have been studied as SCM candidates which can be used as a partial cement replacement, such as: cocoa biomass ash [3], banana leaf ash [4], sugarcane bagasse ash [5], wheat straw bed ash [6], Coffee Husk Ash

(CHA) [7], among others. The use of such ashes in cement matrices meets the requirements of sustainability, economy and ecology required by the current society [8].

Coffee husks are obtained by separating the coffee beans during its process. The Brazilian harvest of 2020 reached a production of 3.72 million tons of processed grains. The amount of coffee husk production is about 45 % of this harvest and, therefore, the amount of husk generated, 1.64 million tons, is remarkable. These residues are usually used to fertilizing coffee crops, as nutritional additive for animals and as fuel in furnaces, where residual ash is produced. However, due to the abundance of this material in Brazil, part of the coffees husks becomes unusable and improperly discarded [8, 9].

These residues are also rich in alkalis, products that can cause undesirable side-effects on the cement matrix, such as the formation of expansive products [10, 11]. Yet, alkalis-rich ashes have been used as cement replacement in cement composites and, depending on the levels of addition of the residue, mechanical properties were not affected, because alkalis were somewhat non-reactive in such ashes [12]. In this context, there is a lack in the knowledge in the specialized literature about the impacts of CHA on the cementitious composites and if it is feasible to use it in an efficient and appropriately manner [7].

In order to answer some of these questions, this work presents the study of hydration kinetics of cement pastes containing different amounts of CHA (0-25 %) as a partial substitute of Portland cement.

2. Methodology

2.1. Burning method of CHA

The used coffee husk species was the Arabica type, obtained at “InovaCafé” (Lavras, Minas Gerais, Brazil). This material was collected after natural outdoor drying and subjected to heat treatment to produce Coffee Husk Ashes (CHA) at 500, 600 and 800 °C for 3 hours in a muffle [7]; the heating rate of this process was 10 °C/min and the cooling occurred naturally with the muffle’s door being opened just 24 hours later. According to residence temperature and time these Coffee Husk Ashes are referred as CHA5003, CHA6003 and CHA8003, respectively.

2.2. Mix design and curing method

The influence of the used CHA in cement pastes with a water to cement ratio (w/c) of 0.4 was evaluated. Six pastes were mixed in a contact vortex mixer for 2 minutes at 3000 rpm, one with just cement and water (reference) and others with cement mass substitution levels of 0 (reference paste, Ref.), 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 % by CHA, by keeping the same w/c. The ashes used in this stage came from the thermal treatment at 600 °C for 3 hours (CHA6003), which moreover showed to be most ecological and presented some amorphism. This material presented, after manual grinding, a continuous granulometry and mean D_{10} , D_{50} and D_{90} diameter values of 7.43, 12.45 and 22.45 μm respectively. The curing age used was 16 hours for the calorimetry test.

The cement used was the Portland cement type CP V, which presented a continuous granulometry and mean D_{10} , D_{50} and D_{90} values of 3.87, 10.25 and 16.68 μm respectively [13].

2.3. Analysis

To determine the percentual chemical composition of the coffee husk ashes, a semi-quantitative analysis by X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) Spectrometry was used in a Titan-Bruker 800N8578 equipment. For this purpose, the

samples were dried and directly analysed using a non-destructive method in a Spectro membrane prolene-thin-film chemplex film paper.

The modified Chapelle test was also used to study the reactivity of the material, that is, to measure the ability to fix lime when kept in an aqueous solution with calcium oxide (CaO) according to NBR 15895 [14].

Finally, aiming at the semi-adiabatic calorimetry test, the pastes, described above, were placed in a thermal box and kept in an acclimatized room (22 °C, 90 % UR) for 24 hours. The temperature curves were obtained by the Data Logger TC-08 equipment and corresponding PicoLog software (Pico Technology, Cambridgeshire, United Kingdom), in order to investigate the hydration kinetics through accumulated heat of the pastes [15].

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) analysis

The elemental quantification of coffee husk ashes CHA5003, CHA6003 and CHA8003, obtained by X-ray Fluorescence XRF is presented in Table 1. The results were compatible with CHA burned at 950 °C carried out by other researches in reference herein [16].

Table 1. XRF of CHA with different thermal treatments and residence time of 3 hours.

Chemical components	CHA5003	CHA6003	CHA8003
	(%)	(%)	(%)
MgO	3.59	4.33	14.63
Al ₂ O ₃	7.32	7.85	4.46
P ₂ O ₅	3.73	4.09	13.31
SO ₃	2.47	3.28	13.33
Cl	4.84	3.26	0.02
K ₂ O	57.35	58.17	20.24
CaO	1.78	2.27	18.42
TiO ₂	-	0.19	0.01
MnO	-	-	0.02
Fe ₂ O ₃	-	0.05	3.05
Minors	0.02	0.01	0.01
Loss on ignition (LOI)	18.91	16.49	12.53

It is observed that most of the heat treatments used did not meet the minimum values of SiO₂ + Al₂O₃ + Fe₂O₃ (70.00 %) and the maximum values of SO₃ (4.00 %), loss on ignition (10.00 %) and Na₂O (1.50 %) to be considered pozzolans. [17]. In addition, the amount of alkalis were high, in all heat treatment conditions, confirming similar results obtained previously [7, 18]. Small amount of calcium is also observed for all the samples. It can also be seen

that, even after 800°C burning condition the LOI value still high, indicating the presence of some volatiles and organic masses such as coke.

3.2. Modified Chapelle test

According to the results of the modified Chapelle test, the value found with the use of CHA6003 was 155.10 g/mg or 15.51 %, which did not reach the minimum recommended value of NBR 12653 [17], which is 75.00 % of CaO fixation. Therefore, the CHA6003 reactivity can be considered as negligible and cannot be considered as a pozzolan. Same results were also found by Lins [7].

3.3. Semi-adiabatic calorimetry

The results from the semi-adiabatic calorimetry test, cumulative heat, can be seen in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Cumulative heat (a) and cumulative heat rate (b) of the pastes.

An increase in the cumulative heat is observed as the presence of CHA in the samples increases (Fig. 1a). The maximum increase was observed for 25 % of CHA content reaching about 7.6 times of that value found for the reference paste. The cumulative heat rate, during the first 40 hours of testing increased from 0.51 J/g.h in the reference paste to 4.41 J/g.h in the paste with 25.00 % of CHA (Fig.1b). Scrivener et al. [19] evaluated that the partial replacement of Portland Cement by SCM leads to an increase in cumulative heat due to the filler effect, that can explain the augments observed on the heat of hydration with the increase in the CHA content in the present research.

4. Conclusions

This work presents the study of the characterization of CHA and the influence of this material as a Portland cement replacement in a cement paste. The following conclusions can be draw: The most abundant elements found in CHA was magnesium, potassium and calcium (alkalis) (XRF test); the analysed CHA did not met the normative specifications to be considered as pozzolan (modified Chapelle test); in the semi-adiabatic calorimetry test, the curves indicated an increase in accumulated heat as the level of CHA in the samples increases.

Given the results found in this research, it is noticeable that the high content of alkalis in the composition of CHA may lead to expansion problems and consequent failures of this type of material. Although, other researches, studding with high-alkali ashes as Portland cement substitutions have not found problems related to that, because alkalis were somewhat non-reactive in such ashes. Still, there is a high potential for its use in geopolymer-based matrices as chemical activators.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Credit author statement

Eduardo Hélio de Novais Miranda: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Data curation; Software; Formal analysis; Resources; Writing - original draft. **Thaiane Oliveira Marcelino:** Conceptualisation; Methodology; Data curation; Software; Formal analysis; Resources; Writing - original draft. **Leonardo Seibert Kuhn:** Writing – review. **Diogo Antonio Correa Gomes:** Writing – review. **Fabício de Campos Vitorino:** Supervision; Writing – review. **Saulo Rocha Ferreira:** Conceptualisation; Methodology; Formal analysis; Resources; Supervision; Writing – review.

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References

- [1] A.P.S.N. Borges et al. Estudo das propriedades de concretos com adição de fibras vegetais e de polipropileno para uso em paredes estruturais. *Matéria (Rio Janeiro)*, Volume 24, 2019. (<https://doi.org/10.1590/S1517-707620190002.0679>).
- [2] ASTM C1897-20, Standard Guide for Evaluation of Alternative Supplementary Cementitious Materials (ASCM) for Use in Concrete. ASTM International, 2005. (<https://www.astm.org>).
- [3] R.B. Silva et al. Cinzas de biomassa geradas na agroindústria do cacau: caracterização e uso em substituição ao cimento. *Ambient. Construído*, Volume 15, 2015. (<https://doi.org/10.1590/s1678-86212015000400053>).
- [4] R.C. Kanning et al. Banana leaves ashes as pozzolan for concrete and mortar of Portland cement. *Construction and Building Materials*, Volume 54, 2014. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2013.12.030>).
- [5] J.S. Le Blond et al. Generation of crystalline silica from sugarcane burning. *Journal of Environmental Monitoring*, Volume 12, 2010. (<https://doi.org/10.1039/c0em00020e>).
- [6] N. M. Al-Akhras. Durability of wheat straw ash concrete to alkali-silica reaction. *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Construction Materials*, Volume 166, 2013. (<https://doi.org/10.1680/coma.11.00005>).
- [7] L.N. Lins. *Estudo da aplicação da casca de café na indústria da construção*. Master's thesis, Universidade Federal Fluminense, 2006. (<http://posciv.uff.br/estudo-da-aplicacao-da-casca-de-cafe-na-industria-da-construcao/>).
- [8] CONAB, *Acompanhamento Da Safra Brasileira 2019/2020*, 2020. (<https://www.conab.gov.br/info-agro/safras>).
- [9] R. Bressani, J.E. Brahan. *Coffee pulp: composition, technology, and utilization*, 1st Edition, 1978. International Development Research Centre. (<https://dl.handle.net/10625/4722%20Date:%201978>).

- [10] I. Jawed, J. Skalny. Alkalies in cement: A review I. Forms of alkalies and their effect on clinker formation. *Cement and Concrete Research*, Volume 7, 1977. ([https://doi.org/10.1016/0008-8846\(77\)90056-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0008-8846(77)90056-4)).
- [11] I. Jawed, J. Skalny. Alkalies in cement: A review: II. Effects of alkalies on hydration and performance of Portland cement. *Cement and Concrete Research*, Volume 8, 1978. ([https://doi.org/10.1016/0008-8846\(78\)90056-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0008-8846(78)90056-X)).
- [12] C.M.A. Fontes et al. Characterization and effect of using bottom and fly ashes from co-combustion of cocoa waste as mineral addition in concrete. *Waste and Biomass Valorization*. Volume 10. (<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-017-0031-x>).
- [13] ABNT NBR 16697, Cimento Portland — Requisitos. Rio de Janeiro. ABNT, 2018. (<https://www.abnt.org.br/>)
- [14] ABNT NBR 15895, Materiais Pozolânicos – Determinação do Teor de Hidróxido de Cálcio Fixado – Método Chapelle Modificado. ABNT, 2010. (<https://www.abnt.org.br/>).
- [15] CEN EN 196-9. Methods of Testing Cement — Part 9: Heat of Hydration — Semi-Adiabatic Method. CEN, 2013. (<https://www.cencenelec.eu/>).
- [16] G. Cruz, P. Crnkovic, P. M. Evaluation of the combustion process of coffee husk samples in a Drop Tube Furnace (DTF). *Revista da Engenharia Térmica*, Volume 14, 2015. (<https://doi.org/10.5380/reterm.v14i2.62135>).
- [17] ABNT NBR 12653, Materiais Pozolânicos — Requisitos. ABNT, 2014. (<https://www.abnt.org.br/>).
- [18] E.D. de Castro. *Aplicação de café nas propriedades de tijolos de solo-cimento*. Master's thesis, Universidade Federal de Lavras, 2017. (<http://www.sbicafe.ufv.br/handle/123456789/11237>).
- [19] K. Scrivener et al. *A Practical Guide to Microstructural Analysis of Cementitious Materials*, 1st Edition, 2017. CRC Press. (<https://doi.org/10.1201/B19074>).